

Thermoelectric properties of organic thin films enhanced by π - π stacking – Supplementary Material

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Self-Assembly of ZnTPP films

Figure S1. (Top) QCM analysis of ZnTPP SAMs grown on Au substrate (logarithmic time scale) and (Bottom) AFM image of ZnTPP by self-assembly with different immersion time, corresponding to points A, B, C and D. (A', D') show the ZnTPP film thickness analysis of by nano-scratching.

Height Distributions of ZnTPP films formed by LB deposition

Figure S2. Height distribution determined AFM nano-scratching of ZnTPP films prepared by Langmuir-Blodgett deposition at surface pressures of (top) 4.8 mN/m, (middle) 12.5 mN/m and (bottom) 18.5 mN/m

ZnTPP samples prepared by thermal sublimation

Samples grown by thermal sublimation used for this work are described in the table below with corresponding AFM topography images given in Figure S3:

Panel of Figure S3	Deposition time (min)	Layer thickness (nm)	Number of layers
a	20	0.3 ± 0.1	1
b	60	1.0 ± 0.2	3 ± 1
c	90	1.5 ± 0.2	5 ± 1
d	200	4.5 ± 0.4	15 ± 2

Table S1. Growth and thickness data for thermal sublimation films of ZnTPP

Figure S3. AFM topographical information for ZnTPP films grown by thermal sublimation with parameters given in Table S1.

Thermovoltage distributions for ZnTPP films

Figure S4. Distribution of thermal voltage vs. ΔT for SAMs based films with (a) 0.4 nm and (b) 1.2 nm thickness.

Figure S5. Thermal voltage vs. ΔT for thermally sublimed films with (a) 0.3 nm, (b) 1.3 nm, (c) 2.1 nm and (d) 4.5 nm thickness,

Figure S6 Thermal voltage vs. ΔT for LB films with (a) 1.4 nm, (b) 2.5 nm and (c) 4.8 nm thickness.